

Maximization of the power delivered from permanent magnet synchronous generator wind energy conversion system to the grid based on using moth flame optimization

Shimaa Aly Hussien^{1,2}, Mahmoud Adel Deab³, Fadwa Alrowais⁴

¹Electrical Department Faculty of Engineering, Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

²Electrical Power and Control Department Pyramids Higher Institute for Engineering and Technology, Giza, Egypt

³Power and Energy Department New Cairo Technological University, Cairo, Egypt

⁴Computer Sciences Department, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jan 20, 2022

Revised Jun 16, 2022

Accepted Jul 14, 2022

Keywords:

Harmony search optimization technique

MATLAB/Simulink

Moth flame optimization technique

Permanent magnet synchronous generator

PSIM

Wind energy conversion system

ABSTRACT

In recent years, optimization techniques have been developed to improve accuracy and reduce execution time. The moth flame optimization (MFO) technique adapts to moth behavior. This design is based on the moth's transverse orientation. Over long distances, they maintain a fixed angle with respect to the moon at night. They spiral around the lights, however. Moths are trapped in a deadly spiral as the light approaches; eventually, they all converge on it. Furthermore, they are created by artificial light and fly similarly. To maximize the power delivered to the grid, moth flame optimization is used to optimize the controller parameters of the wind energy conversion system (WECS). A permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) implements a grid-connected WECS a grid side converter (GSC) and a generator machine side converter (MSC) are used. A simulation package was used to model the proposed model. PSIM software was used to simulate power circuits and converters. Simulations were done in MATLAB. As a result, the obtained controller coefficients minimize both overshoot and steady-state error. Particle swarm optimization (PSO) and harmony search optimization (HSO) results were compared. MFO is a reliable method.

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Corresponding Author:

Shimaa Aly Hussien

Electrical Department Faculty of Engineering, Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University

Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Email: saalebiary@pnu.edu.sa

1. INTRODUCTION

A renewable source of electrical power, wind power can be considered to provide a sustainable source of energy. Its advantage lies in its commercial potential. With the use of renewable energy sources increasing, it has been necessary to develop the integration of the grid and the use of inverters to control frequency, reactive/active power, and to provide grid voltage support [1], [2]. Control techniques have been applied to standalone and grid-connected wind energy conversion systems (WECS) [3], [4]. Machine controllers should be designed to maximize power conversion. Furthermore, grid operators should ensure that reactive power is delivered to the grid as well as active power [5], [6]. WECS utilizes a number of types of generators, including squirrel-cage induction generators, permanent magnet synchronous generators (PMSGs), double fed induction generators (DFIGs), high temperature superconducting synchronous generators (HTS-SGs), and wound rotor synchronous generators.

In order to maximize power extraction from variable speed wind turbines (VSWT), different control methodologies and converters have been implemented. Micro generators were installed, which consist of a wind turbine, an inverter and a generator. The turbines capture the energy and convert it into rotational mechanical energy. Variable speed turbines provide higher energy extraction than constant speed turbines [7]. The generator is responsible for converting mechanical energy into electricity. The benefits of VSWT are numerous, for instance, maximizing the extraction of energy, improving efficiency, increasing power quality, and maximizing power point operation [8], [9]. The use of a direct drive PMSG can improve system performance. This device may be considered as a market leader. It has the advantages of free maintenance due to the absence of brushes, the gearless WECS construction option, and the multi-pole design that provides slow speed operation. A number of reliable controllers have been developed to maximize the harvesting of wind energy [10]-[20], including hill-climb search (HCS), power signal feedback (PSF), and tip speed ratio (TSR). Wind turbine generators must have a variable speed in order to maximize power extraction from fluctuating winds. An inverter/generator control method was implemented. The system consists of two fully controlled 3- Φ converters, one for alternating current (AC)/direct current (DC) power conversion and the other for DC/AC power conversion for grid distribution. MFO [21] is a novel optimization technique that will be implemented to achieve the maximum power in comparison to harmony search optimization (HSO) and particle swarm optimization (PSO) [22], [23].

The paper is organized as follows: the system description is presented in section 1, and the mathematical model is presented in section 2. Section 3 describes the MFO technique. The results are presented in section 4. Section 5 provides the conclusions of the research.

2. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

There are two controllers in the system. Specifically, one controller is located on the generator side converter in order to receive the maximum power from WECS as shown in Figure 1, while the other is located on the grid side inverter in order to transmit the energy. In this paper, four different optimization techniques are used to evaluate the performance of the controller in relation to various quantities. Several parameters must be considered, including power and average power (P_o , Avg. (P_o)), the wind turbine speed and mechanical torque (N_m , T_{em}), generator terminal current (I_{gen}), and grid current (I_{gnd}), and dc-link voltage (V_{dc}). This model consists of a wind turbine, a PMSG, a fully controlled rectifier, a DC link, a fully controlled inverter, and a transmission line to the grid. The PSIM pack simulation is used for the WECS response simulation. For the controller, MATLAB/Simulink was used along with the optimization algorithm simulation [24] as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Illustrates Model

Figure 2. Illustrates model with simulated program

3. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF WECS BASED ON PMSG

Presented in this section is a mathematical model for PMSG based on WECS. A wind energy conversion system consists of a wind turbine, a power management system, and a converter. In order to calculate the wind turbine power in (1) [25]: where wind power is, air density is, coefficient of performance is C_p , swept area is A , and wind speed is. The PMSG dynamic model can be expressed by (1) and (2):

$$P_t = \frac{1}{4} \rho A C_p v_w^3 \tag{1}$$

$$V_d = R_s i_d + \frac{d\lambda_d}{dt} - \omega_e \psi_q \tag{2}$$

$$V_q = R_s i_q + \frac{d\lambda_q}{dt} - \omega_e \psi_d \tag{3}$$

where, d–q axes stator voltage components are V_d and V_q , respectively, and the current components are i_d and i_q , respectively. The d–q stator linkage flux components are ψ_d and ψ_q , respectively. Electric angular rotor speed is ω_e (rad/s). Stator resistance is R_s .

The stator flux linkage components are:

$$\psi_d = L_d i_d + \psi_{Pm} \tag{4}$$

$$\psi_q = L_q i_q \tag{5}$$

where, the stator inductances of the d–q axes are L_d and L_q , respectively. The permanent magnet flux linkage is ψ_{Pm} .

Figure 3 depicts the relationship between the wind turbine speed of the generator (an independent parameter) and the power extracted from the generator (a dependent parameter), where the extracted power is affected by both mechanical and electrical factors. To clarify the relationship between the power extracted at various wind speeds, the parameters of this figure are set at constant values except for the wind speed. On the basis of the curve, the extracted power increased as the turbine speed increased until the maximum power point. After this, the power decreased as the turbine speed increased. The maximum power for each wind speed is different. Maximum tracking should be used when using PowerPoint.

Figure 3. Speed power curve

4. MFO TECHNIQUE APPLIED

MFO is a nature-inspired technique that is based on the behavior of moths. A major source of inspiration for the design was the moth's transverse orientation. At night, they maintain a fixed angle relative to the moon, enabling them to cross long distances in a straight line. Nevertheless, they are typically observed flying in a spiral pattern around the lights. Furthermore, they are created by artificial light and fly in a similar manner. The moth is trapped in a fatal spiral if a light is too close to it. The moths reached toward the light in

the end. The moths' behavior has been mathematically modeled to explain this process of optimization. In the algorithm, the variables are the positions of moths in space, and the solutions are those positions. Consequently, it is possible to travel in one, two, or three dimensions, as well as in overexcited dimensions, and to change the location vectors. Matrix representation of the moth set is as (6).

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} X_{1,1} & X_{1,2} & X_{1,3} & \cdots & X_{1,n} \\ X_{2,1} & X_{2,2} & \cdots & \cdots & X_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots \\ X_{n,1} & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & X_{n,d} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

n: Number of mothes

d: Dimension (Variables)

For sorting the corresponding moths' objective values, the following array is assumed in (7).

$$OX = \begin{bmatrix} OX_1 \\ OX_2 \\ OX_3 \\ \vdots \\ OX_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Fitness value is the return value of each objective function. A position vector is passed to each objective function. A fitness value is assigned to the consistent moth. Flames also play an important role in the introduced technique. A matrix similar to this is presented in (8).

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} f_{1,1} & f_{1,2} & f_{1,3} & \cdots & f_{1,n} \\ f_{2,1} & f_{2,2} & \cdots & \cdots & f_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots \\ f_{n,1} & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & f_{n,d} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

X and F arrays dimensions are equal. To sort the objective values of the flames, an array is assumed as shown in (9).

$$OF = \begin{bmatrix} of_1 \\ of_2 \\ of_3 \\ \vdots \\ of_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Flames and moths differ in the way they move between one another. As the moths move around the search space, flames have proved to be the most advantageous positions so far. It will be updated until a better solution is found, provided that the most suitable solution will not be dropped. MFO provides a three-tuple that is similar to the global optimum of the optimization problems, and is defined as (10).

$$MFO = (J, K, T) \quad (10)$$

Random population function is J. Its model is (11).

$$J: \emptyset \rightarrow \{X, OX\} \quad (11)$$

The function K represents the moth's movement within the search space. It is modeled by an X matrix, and the revenues are updated.

$$K: X \rightarrow X \quad (12)$$

T function continues true only when satisfying termination standard: T: X {true, false}

The ub_i and lb_i matrices express the i th variable upper and lower limits (13).

$$ub_i = [ub_1, ub_2, ub_3, \dots, \dots, ub_n] \quad (13)$$

$$lb_i = [lb_1, lb_2, lb_3, \dots \dots lb_n] \tag{14}$$

Initialization is followed by iterative running for the J function until the T function proceeds. According to the mathematical model, each position is efficient with respect to a flame by (15).

$$X_i = S (X_i , F_n) \tag{15}$$

X_i : indicating the i^{th} moth

F_n : The n^{th} flame is indicated

S: A logarithmic spiral function with the following definition

$$S (X_i , F_n) = D_i . e^{bt} . \cos(2\pi t) + F_n \tag{16}$$

where,

D_i : indicates the distance between the i -th moth and the n -th flame

b : A constant that defines the shape of the logarithmic spiral

t : a random number between [1, 1].

D : can be calculated as (17).

$$D_i = |F_n - X_i| \tag{17}$$

Thus, an ellipse is predicted in all directions around the flame, and the moth's next position would fall within this ellipse. Therefore, the search space can be exploited and explored with certainty. Figure 4 shows the algorithm flow diagram.

Figure 4. MFO Flow chart

5. SIMULATION RESULTS FOR THE PROPOSED TECHNIQUES

Simulink and PSIM simulations using a Rung Kutta fixed-step solver yield the best results when the sampling time is simulated at 5s and the total simulation time is 0.2s. PSIM was used to simulate the power circuit, while MATLAB/Simulink was used to simulate the optimization technique and the control system. A

summary of the characteristics of the wind turbine is presented in Table 1 and a summary of the PMSG parameters is shown in Table 2. Three optimization algorithms were implemented and compared in order to determine the optimal controller parameters. As a result, grid-delivered power would be optimized. In order to determine the most appropriate method.

Table 1. Wind turbine characteristics

Parameter	Values
Input for blade pitch angle	0
Inertial moment power	1 kg.m ²
Power nominal output wind	19 kW
Wind speed at base	12 m/s
Rotational speed at base	190 rpm

Table 2. PMSG parameters

Parameter	Values
L_q (q-axis inductance)	1 mH
L_d (d-axis inductance)	1 mH
Moment of inertia	100 kg m ²
R_s (stator resistance)	1 Ω
P (Poles Number)	30

As shown in Figures 5, the simulation results for the system with a speed of 12 m/s are presented. The purpose of this study is to determine which technique is most effective. The following subfigures illustrate the system response: Figures 5(a) grid delivered power and its average; Figures 5(b) turbine torque and speed; Figures 5(c) 3- Φ generator current; Figures 5(d) 3- Φ grid current; and Figures 5(e) DC link voltage.

Figure 5. Results of the simulation for MFO (a) the grid delivered power and its average; (b) Torque and speed of the turbine; (c) 3- Φ generator current; (d) 3- Φ grid current; (e) A voltage of the DC link

As shown in Figures 6, the simulation results for the system with a speed of 12 m/s are presented. The purpose of this study is to determine which technique is most effective. The following subfigures illustrate the system response: Figure 6(a) grid delivered power and its average; Figure 6(b) turbine torque and speed; Figure 6(c) 3- Φ generator current; Figure 6(d) 3- Φ grid current; and Figure 6(e) DC link voltage.

As shown in Figures 7, the simulation results for the system with a speed of 12 m/s are presented. The following subfigures illustrate the system response: Figure 7(a) grid delivered power and its average; Figure 7(b) turbine torque and speed; Figure 7(c) 3- Φ generator current; Figure 7(d) 3- Φ grid current; and Figure 7(e) DC link voltage.

In Figure 8, three power curves are illustrated, namely the grid-delivered power curve and the DC-link voltage curve. The MFO response with the lowest maximum positive overshoot reached steady state the quickest. Figure 9 illustrates a comparison of the DC-link voltage between the three techniques.

It is noticeable that the system response with MFO remains stable at 605 V without change, resulting in an accurate output response. The results of the speed and torque of the turbine for the three techniques are similar with few changes as shown in Figures 10 and 11.

Figure 6. Results of the simulation for HSO (a) the grid delivered power and its average; (b) Torque and speed of the turbine; (c) 3- Φ generator current; (d) 3- Φ grid current; (e) A voltage of the DC link

Figure 7. Results of the simulation for PSO (a) the grid delivered power and its average; (b) Torque and speed of the turbine; (c) 3- Φ generator current; (d) 3- Φ grid current; (e) A voltage of the DC link

Figure 8. Grid power delivered for all three techniques

Figure 9. DC voltage of the DC link in the three techniques

Figure 10. Wind turbine torque for the three techniques

Figure 11. The wind turbine speed for the three techniques

6. CONCLUSIONS

A double controller that is used with the PMSG on WECS is optimized using the MFO technique in this paper. MATLAB/Simulink was used to simulate the controllers and three optimization techniques, and PSIM was used to simulate the converters and power circuits. A fully controlled generator side converter, a direct drive turbine without a gearbox, and a fully controlled inverter are included. The grid-side converter was controlled to enhance power quality, whereas the generator-side converter was controlled to maximize the amount of power extracted. Our research has compared the results of three optimization techniques in order to arrive at optimum controller parameters, namely MFO, HSO, and PSO. A MFO technique achieved

optimal parameters that were more accurate than others, with an output power signal with minimal overshoot and a DC link voltage that was more stable. A double controller WECS combined with PMSG could be used with the MFO technique in order to maximize grid power delivery.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research project was funded by the Deanship of Scientific Research, Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University, through the Program of Research Project Funding After Publication, grant No (41-PRFA-P-37).

FUNDING

This research was funded by the Deanship of Scientific Research, Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University, through the Program of Research Project Funding After Publication, grant No (41-PRFA-P-37).

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Shima Aly Hussien was born in 1986, Giza, Egypt. She received the B.Sc., M.Sc. and Ph.D. degree in Electrical Power and Machines, Faculty of Engineering, Banha University, Egypt, in 2008, 2013 and 2017, respectively. Starting from September 2009, she worked as a teaching assistant, then as an Assistant Professor in Electrical Power and Control Department, Pyramids Higher Institute for Engineering and Technology, Giza, Egypt. In 2018, she worked as Assistant Professor in Electrical Power Department, Princess Nora University. Her research interests include power systems, energy management systems, renewable energy, smart grid, optimization, batteries and control. She can be contacted at email: saalebiary@pnu.edu.sa.

Mahmoud Adel Deab was born in 1986, Cairo, Egypt. He received the B.Sc., M.Sc. and Ph.D. degree in Electrical Power and Machines, Faculty of Engineering, Banha University, Egypt, in 2008, 2013 and 2017, respectively. Starting from September 2009, he worked as a teaching assistant, then as an Assistant Professor in Electrical Power and Control Department, Pyramids Higher Institute for Engineering and Technology, Giza, Egypt. In 2019, he works in Renewable Energy Department, Faculty of Engineering and Energy, New Cairo Technological University. His research interests include power systems, energy management systems, control of power system. He can be contacted at email: Dr.madaeb@gmail.com.

Fadwa Alrowais received the B.Sc. degree (Hons.) in computer and information sciences in the field of computer applications and the M.Sc. degree in computer science from the College of Computer and Information Sciences, King Saud University, Saudi Arabia, in 1996 and 2005, respectively, and the Ph.D. degree in computer science from the Faculty of Electronics and Computer Sciences, Southampton University, U.K., in 2016. She has 23 years academic experience, as she has worked with the College of Computer and Information Sciences, Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University, and with the College of Engineering. She can be contacted at email: fmalrowais@pnu.edu.sa.